

Synthesis of Bis-(glyoxalimine) N,N'-di (L, L') Glutaric Acid and Studies in its Metal-Chelates

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Synthesis of a new multidentate chelating agent Bis-(glyoxal imine) N, N', di (L, L') glutaric acid is reported. The acid base equilibria and metal ion chelating tendency of the ligand with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) is also reported. The acid dissociation constants of the ligand, the stability constants of the Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes in an ionic medium of 0.1M NaClO₄ at a temperature of 30° ± 1° have been calculated. The probable structure of these complexes have also been suggested. The free energy of complex formation is also reported for each metal ion.

KLIGMAN¹ *et al.* have recently reported the condensation of glyoxal and anthranilic acid. The condensation product have been shown to have the cyclic structure (I) [2,2' bis(1,2-dihydro-4-oxo-3,1 benzoxine)] instead of the expected diamino product (II) [N, N' bis (carboxyl phenyl) ethane diamine].

Mathur *et al.*² have reported this compound as a stereospecific reagent and have suggested that the complexation with the metal involves in the first step, the metal catalysed hydrolysis of the ligand which is followed by complexation with the metal. The work reported here was undertaken with a view to attempt condensation of glutamic acid with glyoxal and to study the metal chelating properties of the new ligand.

Experimental

Synthesis of Bis (glyoxal imine) N, N' di (L, L') glutaric acid :

The reagent was prepared by refluxing the gm molecular quantities of L. glutamic acid and glyoxal

in the ratio of 2 : 1 for ca 24 hr. at 50°-52° in presence of few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The resultant liquid was cooled to room temperature and then filtered. The reagent was crystallised from the filtrate and recrystallised with water.

The percentage analysis of the compound showed C, 44.84 (found) 45.57 (Calc.); N, 8.65 (found) 8.86 (Calc.) and H 5.00 (found) 5.06 (Calc.) m.p. was 184°.

Ligand solution :

A 0.02 M ligand solution was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity in warm water and then diluting as necessary.

Solution of Metal ions :

Analytical grade Cu(NO₃)₂, Ni(NO₃)₂ and Co(NO₃)₂ were used, the solutions were standardised³ and were diluted to 0.02 M solution.

Sodium hydroxide solution :

Approximately molar solution of carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardised with A.R. potassium hydrogen phthalate solution. It was then diluted to M/2.54.

Potentiometric method :

The pH titrations of the ligand with standard alkali solution in the absence and presence of metal ions were carried out by using a Photovolt pH meter reading up to 0.002 pH unit. The pH meter was standardised before and checked after each titration with buffer solutions of pH 4.0 and 7.0. The electrode system was glass-calomel.

Calculations

Dissociation constants of the ligand : (Bjerrum⁴ method)

The dissociation constants of the ligand were calculated graphically by plotting a graph between \bar{n}_H and pH.

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$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{4H_4A + 3H_3A^- + 2H_2A^{-2} + HA^{-3}}{H_4A + H_3A^- + H_2A^{-2} + HA^{-3} + A^{-4}}$$

$$\bar{n}_H = \frac{4C_A - (Na^+ + H^+ - OH^-)}{C_A}$$

where

\bar{n}_H = average number of protons bound per ligand ion.

C_A = Total ligand concentration

Na^+ = Conc. of the base added.

From a plot of \bar{n}_H vs. pH , the pH values corresponding to $\bar{n}_H = 3.5, 2.5, 1.5, 0.5$ gives the values of pK_1, pK_2, pK_3, pK_4 respectively.

Calculations of metal chelate stability constants :

The metal chelate stability constants were calculated by (i) modified Bjerrum method and (ii) algebraic method.

Modified Bjerrum method :

$\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were calculated from the formation curve obtained by plotting \bar{n} against $-\log A^{-4}$. The $\log A^{-4}$ values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 gives $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively.

\bar{n} = Average number of moles of ligand bound per metal ion.

$$= \frac{C_A - [A^{-4}]Y}{C_M}$$

where C_A and C_M are the total ligand and metal ion concentration respectively.

A^{-4} = equilibrium concentration of the ligand and is calculated by the expression

$$A^{-4} = \frac{(4-a)C_A - [H^+] + [OH^-]}{X}$$

$$\text{where } X = \frac{4[H^{+4}]}{K_1K_2K_3K_4} + \frac{3[H^{+3}]}{K_2K_3K_4} + \frac{2[H^{+2}]}{K_3K_4} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_4}$$

$$\text{and } Y = \frac{[H^{+4}]}{K_1K_2K_3K_4} + \frac{[H^{+3}]}{K_2K_3K_4} + \frac{[H^{+2}]}{K_3K_4} + \frac{[H^+]}{K_4} + 1$$

K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 are the acid dissociation constants of the ligand.

For 1 : 1 titration curves the $\log K_1$ values were also calculated by algebraic method applying the following equation

$$K = \frac{C_A - Y[A^{-4}]}{[A^{-4}]\{C_M + Y[A^{-4}] - C_A\}}$$

Calculation of heat of formation :

The heats of formation ($-\Delta F$) of 1 : 1 complex were calculated by using the relation

$$\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K.$$

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants (pK_1, pK_2, pK_3 and pK_4) of the ligand at 30° ($\mu = 0.1$) were found to be 3.72, 4.54, 8.90 and 9.81 respectively.

The stability constants of the metal complexes and the free energy of complex formation are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1. METAL CHELATE STABILITY CONSTANT AND FREE ENERGY OF COMPLEX FORMATION

Metal	Graphical method		Algebraic method	$-\Delta F^\circ$ K Cal/°C/ mole
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log K_1$	
Cu(II)	12.4	7.1	12.32	17.3
Ni(II)	9.25	—	9.21	12.8
Co(II)	6.1	—	6.08	8.5

The ligand titration curve shows a strong inflection at $a = 2$ and a weak inflection at $a = 4$. The lower buffer region upto $a = 2$ corresponds to the neutralisation of the two strongly acidic protons and the higher buffer region between $a = 2$ to $a = 4$ corresponds to the neutralisation of the weakly acidic ammonium protons (zwitter ions). The absence of any inflection between $a = 0$ to 2 and that between $a = 2$ to 4 suggests that the acid dissociation equilibria are overlapping. The various neutralisation steps may be represented as under—

The 1 : 1 titration curve : (Fig. 1)

The addition of equivalent amount of the metal ion to the ligand greatly lowers the higher buffer region between $a = 2$ to $a = 4$ in all the three cases. In the case of copper however, there is also a lowering in the lower buffer region. In case of Ni the 1 : 1 complex is formed between pH 5 to 9.4 and that

in the case of Co(II) is formed between pH 5 to 8.75. The 1 : 1 copper complex is stable between the pH range of 3 to 9.5. The two complex forming equilibria are represented as under :

1.2 Titration curves : (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal ligand ratio (total vol = 40 ml).

- Curves —(1) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand.
 (2) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 10 ml of Co(II)
 (3) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 10 ml of Ni(II)
 (4) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 10 ml of Cu(II)
 (5) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 5 ml of Co(II)
 (6) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 5 ml of Ni(II)
 (7) 10 ml of 0.02M ligand + 5 ml of Cu(II).

Copper : The 1 : 2 metal ligand titration curve (Fig. 1) shows a lowering in the lower buffer region indicating the interaction of the metal with the neutral ligand species. The curve shows a slopping buffer region up to $\alpha = 3$ and at $\alpha = 3$. There is a strong inflection. This suggests that the 1 : 1 complex formation is complete at $\alpha = 3$ in accordance with the following equilibria :

The 1 : 1 complex formation is complete at pH = 8.75 beyond which the slopping buffer region between $\alpha = 3-4$ corresponding to pH 8.75-10 indicates the formation of a 1 : 2 copper ligand complex in accordance with the following equilibria

Ni(II) and Co(II) : The 1 : 2 metal ligand titration curves show no acidification effect in the lower buffer region i.e., no complexation up to a pH of 5.5 ($\alpha = 2$). There is a steep rise of pH from $\alpha = 2$

(pH = 5.5) to $\alpha = 3$ (pH = 8.75); in this region a strong 1 : 1 complex is formed in accordance with the following equations.

Beyond pH = 8.75, there is a slopping buffer region between $\alpha = 3$ to $\alpha = 4$ corresponding to the formation of a 1 : 2 complex according to the following equations.

The 1 : 2 complex formation in all the three cases is further substantiated by the fact that the 1 : 2 metal ligand curves in the higher buffer region are some what lower than the ligand curve.

Formation curves (Fig. 2)

The formation curves (\bar{n} Vs $-\log A^{-4}$) for Cu(II) Co(II) and Ni(II) are shown in Fig. 2. The sharp inflection at $\bar{n} = 1$ in the case of copper(II) indicates that there is no overlapping in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complex formation.

Fig. 2 Formation curve for metal-ligand system. (1 copper, 2 nickel, 3 cobalt.)

The degree of formation \bar{n} does not proceed far for Co(II) and Ni(II) it is therefore apparent that there is a considerable overlapping in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes in case of Co(II) and some overlapping in case Ni(II).

Because of the uncertainty in the values of the stability constants of 1 : 2 complexes on account of considerable overlapping in the case of Co(II) and Ni(II) the values of $\log K_2$ for these metal ions are not reported. The order of the chelate stability constants follow the Irving William series $\text{Cu}^{+2} > \text{Ni}^{+2} > \text{Co}^{+2}$. The probable structure of 1 : 1 complex may be represented as follows :

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